

Speculation on Gibbs' Paradox Part 3

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The notion of identical particles is used in the maximization of entropy (MaxEnt), subject to constraints, approach of deriving the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. Thus, if this MaxEnt approach is correct, one should treat particles as indistinguishable when considering macrostates and entropy. This does not mean that physically the particles are necessarily indistinguishable, they are simply indistinguishable to the interactions which occur in the particular statistical model considered, namely an ideal gas in the Sackur-Tetrode entropy situation.

When calculating entropy, given that $-\ln(V^N)$ is the raw number of volume states (which allows all particles to be on one side or the other of V and all other arrangements), one should divide by $N!$, i.e. use $-\ln(V^N / N!)$ to enforce indistinguishability. This is essentially the Sackur-Tetrode result if one uses the first order Stirling approximation and it is consistent with the MaxEnt approach which is necessary. Now, based on the Sackur-Tetrode result, a gas with N particles, T and volume V has the same entropy as two boxes each with $N/2$, $V/2$, T or three boxes with $N/3$, $V/3$, T etc or even combinations such that the density in each box is the same as that of V , N , T and the temperature as well. (We will argue that this only follows because the first order Stirling's approximation is used. Physically, the extensivity of entropies of an ideal gas is an approximation.)

The point we made in Part 1, however, is that two boxes of $N/2$, $V/2$, T particles are constrained and entropy increases even if particles are indistinguishable if one removes a partition separating the two boxes. It is only the scenario that of N particles, $N/2$ particles are on one side of V and $N/2$ on the other that the set of macrostates match the product of states of each $V/2$, $N/2$, T , if indistinguishability is applied. The entropy of the V, N, T set goes as $\ln(V^N / N!)$. This allows for all arrangements of indistinguishable particles, i.e. all N particles on one side of V or the other etc. This is the full entropy linked with $\ln(V^N / N!)$ and this includes states which are not in the two box $N/2$, $V/2$, T picture because in that case there must be $N/2$ particles in each box, i.e. each $V/2$ region.

The point we make is that the first order Stirling's approximation $\ln(N!) \approx N \ln(N)$ is used in obtaining the Sackur-Tetrode equation (just as it is used in MaxEnt) and so an approximation appears. It is not the case that the overall entropy $\ln(V^N / N!)$ is the same as $2 * \ln(V/2^{N/2} / (N/2)!)$. This equality only happens through the first order Stirling approximation (which is used to derive the Sackur-Tetrode equation). This seems to favour pictures of equal density in V, N, T and ignore cases of more particles on one side of the box or the other. This first order Stirling's approximation is the reason for 2^* entropy of a $V/2$, $N/2$, T box equals that of N, V, T .

In reality, the entropies are not the same if one does not use Stirling's approximation taken to first order. Mathematically it is trivial to see that for $N=4$ (small number so Stirling's approximation does not hold) $V^4 / 4! > (V/2)^2 / 2! * (V/2)^2 / 2!$. As a result, we argue that the entropy of two $V/2$, $N/2$, T gases increases when a partition is removed even for identical particles because one restricts $N/2$ particles into one side $V/2$. If one has N, T, V and

inserts a partition, one does not know how many particles are on the right or left and so there is no decrease in entropy we argue.

Using the Sackur-Tetrode equation which is based on the first order of the first order Stirling approximation yields the approximation that the entropy of two $V/2, N/2, T$ is equivalent to that of V, N, T and so there is not issue about adding or removing a partition. Strictly speaking, however, the entropy of two $N/2, V/2, T$ boxes is less than that of V, N, T (even for identical particles) while starting with V, N, T and adding a partition does not increase entropy because one does not know how particles end up in each box (even for identical particles).

In other words, extensivity of Maxwell-Boltzmann entropy only holds if one uses the first order Stirling's approximation. Physically, the entropy is not extensive and the extensivity starts to break down if one uses the third order Stirling's approximation.

Indistinguishability of Particles

We consider N particles in V with T and argue that the particles should be treated as indistinguishable for the maximization of entropy approach to work. In particular, one considers an entropy function of:

$$\ln \left(\frac{N!}{\prod_i n_i!} \right) \quad ((1))$$

This is maximized subject to

$$\sum_i p_i = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i e_i p_i = E_{ave} \quad ((2))$$

We note that the first order Stirling's approximation is used, i.e.

$$\ln(n!) = n \ln(n) \quad ((3))$$

As a result, the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution which results is an approximation because Stirling's approximation is one.

We have pointed out before that describing particles as identical does not necessarily mean that this follows from quantum mechanics, It simply means that they interact as identical particles.

The fact that particles are considered indistinguishable in the MaxEnt (maximization of entropy) approach means that they must be considered identical when considering macrostates. This leads us to the comparison of a V, N, T state with two $V/2, N/2, T$ states.

Entropy in Terms of Identical States

The entropy of a N particles in V with T goes as:

$$\ln(V^N / N!) + \ln(T^N) + \text{constant} \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is essentially the Sackur-Tetrode equation if one uses the first order Stirling's approximation:

$$\ln(n!) = n \ln(n) \quad ((5))$$

The Sackur-Tetrode entropy is an approximation just like the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is an approximation. Both are based on the first order Stirling's approximation. We suggest that this approximation is a key feature because the entropy of two $N/2, V/2, T$ gases is the same as an N, V, T one only in the first order Stirling approximation (and second order as well, but not third).

In particular, one may see that considering V power $N / N!$ For $N=4$ and two cases with $N=2$ yields:

$$V \text{ power } 4 / 24 > (V/2) \text{ power } 2 / 2 * (V/2) \text{ power } 2/2 = V \text{ power } 4 / 64 \quad ((6))$$

((6)) suggests that the entropy of two $V/2, N/2, T$ boxes is less than that of a single V, N, T box which it should be. The V power $N / N!$ Equation means that all positioning in the V box is possible, i.e. N particles may all be on the right or left etc even with identical particles. ((6)) uses identical particles and shows that the number of macrostates are not the same for two $V/2, N/2, T$ cases versus a single V, N, T .

We suggest that it must be the first order Stirling approximation which makes it seem that the entropy of two $N/2, V/2, T$ boxes is the same as that of a single V, N, T case,

$$\ln(V \text{ power } N / N!) = N \ln(V) - N \ln(N) \quad ((7))$$

((7)) is exactly what appears in the Sackur-Tetrode entropy equation (1):

$$S/N = \ln(V/N [4*3.14*m U / (3hhN)] \text{ power } 1.5) + 5/2 \quad ((8))$$

One may see that:

$$N \ln(V) - N \ln(N) = 2 * [N/2 \ln(V/2) - N/2 \ln(N/2)] \quad ((9))$$

This follows from the first order Stirling's approximation. To third order, the Stirling's approximation is:

$$n! \text{ approx} = \exp(n \ln(n)) \exp(-n) \sqrt{2*3.14*n} \quad ((10))$$

$$\text{If one uses: } \ln(n!) = n \ln(n) \text{ or } \ln(n!) = n \ln(n) - n \quad ((11))$$

then the two $V/2, N/2, T$ cases have the same entropy as the single V, N, T case. If one includes the third order term $.5 \ln(n)$, they do not. In other words, the Sackur-Tetrode entropy is only extensive because one uses the first order Stirling approximation. In reality, it is not extensive

and the full expression $\ln(V^N / N!)$ shows this as does the third order Stirling's approximation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one should consider particles as indistinguishable when considering Maxwell-Boltzmann (ideal gas) entropy because one considers them indistinguishable when using MaxEnt (maximization of entropy subject to constraints) i.e. $\ln(N! / \prod_i n_i!)$. The key idea is that one uses Stirling's approximation to first order i.e. $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$.

We argue that using indistinguishability for macrostates yields the number of macrostates being proportional to $V^N / N!$. One may immediately see that the number of macrostates for $N=4$, V is more than that for two sets of $N=2$, $V/2$ with both at the same T , as it should be, i.e. $V^4 / 24 > (V/2)^4 / 64$. The problem is that the Sackur-Tetrode entropy equation states that the sum of entropies for two $N/2$, $V/2$, T systems adds to that of a single V , N , T . Physically the sum of entropies is less than that of the V , N , T system, but we argue that the equality arises because one uses the first order of Stirling's approximation (just as in the MaxEnt case which yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution). It is only if one goes to third order in the Stirling's approximation that one sees that the entropy for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case is not extensive. If one has two $N/2$, $V/2$, T gases, the entropy increases if one removes the partition (but it stays the same according to the first order Stirling approximation Sackur-Tetrode equation). If one has an N , V , T gas, adding a partition does not change entropy for identical particles because each macrostate maps to a product state for each gas because one does not know how many particles end up in each $V/2$, as argued in Part 1.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sackur%E2%80%93Tetrode_equation
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stirling%27s_approximation